

Community-Driven Development of Infrastructure Use Cases in NFDI-MatWerk

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Abstract

Digital transformation in Materials Science and Engineering (MSE) hinges on scalable, interoperable, and community-driven research data infrastructures. To achieve this, NFDI-MatWerk introduces Infrastructure Use Cases (IUCs) [1], [2]. These IUCs stem from a requirement analysis of the MSE community where key challenges were identified: harmonization of data formats, documentation of contextual information, interoperable software tools, and implementation of FAIR principles [3]. The IUCs serve as research-relevant profiles for the development and validation of a sustainable research data infrastructure. They are continuously refined through an iterative process involving community feedback, ensuring the infrastructure remains aligned with evolving user requirements.

We present the results of four IUCs, selected for their community relevance and broad applicability across multiple research scenarios. We have developed demonstrators that showcase research data workflows. These demonstrators serve multiple purposes: validate the technical feasibility of our infrastructure, offer concrete examples of FAIR data principles in practice, and support knowledge transfer across the community by illustrating best practices in data harmonization and evaluation.

Each demonstrator represents the IUC's core objectives:

- IUC02: Framework for curation and distribution of reference datasets.

The use case describes reference data for creep testing, a method to determine time-dependent deformation of a material under constant load at elevated temperatures. The data must meet high standards of completeness, documentation, and measurement precision [4]. In our demonstrator, these requirements are addressed through metadata schema, ontology, and SHACL shapes for validation, specifying mandatory entries and data types. The goal is to populate a local database with validated, searchable data compatible with other databases.

- IUC04: Data Integration for the construction of Defect Phase Diagrams.

The aim of the IUC and its key participant project CRC-1394 is to extend bulk phase diagrams to defect phase diagrams for predicting material properties. This requires managing large volumes of experimental and computational data. We showcase how data from diverse sources can be seamlessly collected using tools built around openBIS, an electronic laboratory notebook and laboratory information management system, creating a cohesive research data management ecosystem. Relevant metadata were identified through a community effort [5] and are currently being refined and extended. Automated metadata extraction supports data sharing across a large interdisciplinary collaboration.

- IUC09: Reproducible data analyses workflows for atom probe tomography (APT).

APT is widely used for nanoscale structure and composition characterization in materials science, geosciences, and biological sciences. Standardized workflows for analysis and post-processing are essential to enable interoperability across software tools from different research communities. In collaboration with FAIRmat [6], we demonstrate reproducible APT workflows that integrate different analysis tools. This is a key step toward automating FAIR data production and advancing reproducible scientific analysis in the field.

- IUC17: Ontologies for crystal defects and integration with simulation workflows.

In materials science, studying crystalline structures and defects is crucial for understanding material properties. However, simulation and experimental data often lack standardized annotation, making it difficult to compare, share, and reuse. The goal is to develop ontologies for crystallographic defects that can be applied consistently across length scales. The demonstrator focuses on atomistic simulations. It addresses the challenge of inconsistent data annotation through the development of atomRDF [7], an ontology-based metadata annotation tool. By semantically structuring simulation data, this approach improves data interoperability and reusability.

These demonstrators not only address community-identified needs, but also promote shared understanding of digital workflows in MSE. Our iterative development process aims to ensure long-term alignment with scientific practices while also enabling future scalability of the research data infrastructure.

Keywords: Materials Science and Engineering, Infrastructure Use Case, Research Data Management

Resources

IUC02

- IUC02 demonstrator: <https://iuc02-7a8113ce3b62.herokuapp.com/>. Workflow that collects and maps data to a metadata schema, instantiates an ontology and generates a data graph that undergoes automated SHACL-based validation.
- Data schema for creep data: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11668375>. Structured metadata for required information on a creep experiment using the terminology of the corresponding standard and agreed upon by domain experts.
- BAM Reference Data: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13937987>. This publication provides comprehensive metadata and test results of constant force creep tests according to DIN EN ISO 204:2019-4 on single crystal Ni-based superalloys.

IUC04

- Companion App demonstrator: <https://nfdimatwerk-iuc04-demo.streamlit.app>. An account in the openBIS instance hosted at <https://openbis.imm.rwth-aachen.de/openbis/webapp/eln-lims/> is needed.
- Companion App for the openBIS ELN-LIMS: <https://hub.docker.com/r/rwthimm/openbis-companion>. A Python-based web application used to integrate experimental data, for use in a Materials Science and Engineering Laboratory.
- openBIS Schema Extension for Materials Science and Engineering: https://git.rwth-aachen.de/Kerzel/openbis_materialsscience_schema/. A set of Python scripts allowing the rapid customization of a fresh openBIS installation.
- pyiron_atomistics: https://github.com/pyiron/pyiron_atomistics. Workflows enabled by interface to atomistic simulation codes.

IUC09

- IUC09 demonstrator: <https://go.fair-workflows.org/iuc09>. A web-based instance for the demonstration of the workflows for APT analysis.
- CompositionSpace: <https://github.com/eisenforschung/CompositionSpace>. Software tool for APT data analysis.
- paraprobe-toolbox: <https://gitlab.com/paraprobe/paraprobe-toolbox>. Software tool for APT data analysis.
- pyiron_apt: https://github.com/pyiron/pyiron_apt. Workflows for APT data analysis.
- pyiron_workflow: https://github.com/pyiron/pyiron_workflow. Graph and node based workflow composition and management tool.

IUC17

- IUC17 demonstrator: <https://go.fzj.de/iuc17>. Jupyter notebooks illustrating usage of the ontologies and atomRDF in creating and querying atomic structures for atomistic simulations.
- OCDO organization: <https://github.com/OCDO>. Open Crystallographic Defects Ontologies (OCDO) is a GitHub organization where the ontologies developed are hosted. Specifically: Computational Materials Sample Ontology, Atomistic Simulation Methods Ontology, and Crystallographic Defect Ontology Suite.
- atomRDF: <https://github.com/pyscal/atomRDF>. A Python tool for ontology-based creation, manipulation, and querying of atomic structures.

Author contributions

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IUC17 - Conceptualization: A. Azócar Guzmán, S. Menon, T. Hickel. Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft: A. Azócar Guzmán, S. Menon. Funding acquisition, Supervision: T. Hickel, S. Sandfeld. Writing – review & editing: A. Azócar Guzmán, S. Menon, S. Sandfeld.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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